

Emotion and Design in Theatrical Performances

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Abstract

The paper presents a case study - part of the design research dialogues between the Interior Design Department of the Technological Educational Institution of Athens and the Budapest University of Craft and Design. It investigates the possibility of incorporating the powers of design driven emotions in theatrical performances – a special and specific field that emotions play a catalytic role. It is also an exchange of ideas and information on emotion influenced design and an alternative experience and approach to Hellenic theatrical performances through design education. The research team faced this new challenge in the applied research direction, by exploring connections within the areas of design, emotion, theater and modern technology. The use of modern technology played a vital and no-replaceable role. The participating students presented a silent Archaic drama, where design and emotion substitute the words, embodying actors and scenery, creating a magical and altogether mythical atmosphere, so that the eyes become gates for feelings and emotions.

Key words: Theatrical Design – Emotion - Design Practice.

Introduction

Inspiration and starting point of our research work was the cultural dialogue that started in 2001 between the Faculty of Interior Design of the Technological Educational Institution (TEI) of Athens and the Textile Design Department of the Magyar Iparművészeti Egyetem, (Hungarian University of Craft and Design), and involved Hungarian and Greek design professors, and Greek participating students with their design works. The first presentation of the “Pattern Theatre” by the Budapest University of Craft and Design, that took place in the Faculty of Interior Design of TEI of Athens, established the basis of our design research synergy. TEI of Athens is increasingly open to new relationships and collaborations with other Educational Institutions in the field of design research, and the project was a real challenge for our research team and a way to exchange insights, research tools and methods that support research. Thus both parties would strongly benefit from learning about their mutual design approaches and experimentations.

Emotion and Hellenic Drama

The definition of emotion was a vital first step for our students in order to understand its powers within the design process. Emotion derives from the Latin word *emovere*. During the centuries hundreds of philosophers and researchers have tried to give an exact definition of

emotion without the greatest success. The only common ground among a myriad of writers is the conclusion that emotion is not easy to define (Richins 1997). The first thinking on the physiological basis of emotions is due to Aristotle and his followers, “The Peripatites”, who introduced the concept of emotional expression as part of emotional experience. The philosophical analysis of emotion was a major problem of the philosophers of the ancient world too, from Heraclitus, Anaxagoras, Empedocles, Diogenes, Heraclitus, Democritus, Hippocrates, to Socrates and Plato. They analysed the meaning, the influence and the results of emotion. From the fact that “Humans think and feel with their body” – Empedocles – to Democritus statement that “Happiness (positive emotion) is characterized by a state of mental and physical equilibrium”, we identify their continuous search to understand and define emotion.

In the third century BC, Aristotle considered emotion an experiencing and evaluating stimulus. This definition represents the first signs of dualism, the belief that mind and body are two completely different entities. For two thousand years the emotion concept did not change measurably. In the seventeenth century, Descartes thought that emotion mediated between a stimulus and a response, introducing the transformation of the duality of mind-body to a soul-body relation (Strongman 1978). Researchers suggest a more comprehensive definition: "Emotion is a complex set of interactions among subjective and objective factors, mediated by neural/hormonal systems, which can: give rise to affective experiences, generate cognitive processes, activate widespread physiological adjustments, lead to behaviour that is often expressive, goal directed, and adaptive" (Kleinginna and Kleinginna 1981:355). According to the dictionary emotion is: any strong feeling - pleasing or painful, a moving of the mind caused by specific causes and is manifested by sensible effects on the body, a mental state that arises spontaneously and is often accompanied by physiological changes, a feeling, (Encyclopaedia Domi:275).

Is there any relation between emotion and Hellenic drama? Emotion was the inspiration and the strategic centum of the myth for all the Hellenic dramatic writers, so Hellenic drama was a most suitable platform for our research to experiment on emotional design. It is the nature, the myth and structure of archaic drama that makes it an emotional catalyst for all those who study it or attend it, and much more for all those who work with it. The very essence of theatrical literature is a continuous war between emotion and intellect. Ancient drama – tragedy mainly but also comedy presents men in action under positive or negative emotions,

and through pity, fear, happiness and laugh the relief and the solutions do happen. It is historically and actively proven, that theatre, through these emotional inputs, emphasized pedagogy, idealism and harmony.

Is there any relation between modern theatre and Hellenic drama? The comedy and tragedy which developed in Athens and flourished in the fifth and fourth centuries BC have influenced nearly all subsequent Western drama, starting with that of the Romans. The Romans, with their love of spectacle took over the existing theatres in Greece for their own spectacles, which included everything from pantomime to mock- naval battles. Opera owes its existence to an attempt to get back to the Greeks. French classical tragedy and 19th- and 20th-century Irish drama both feature Greek themes. Even Brecht wrote an *Antigone*, and Jules Dassin's film 'A Dream of Passion' is based on Euripides' *Medea*. In our modern period many television programs hearken back to the topical humour of Aristophanes. *Commedia dell' arte* bears a strong resemblance to Roman comedy. The modern proscenium theatre evolved from misinterpretations of the Roman architect Vitruvius' descriptions of theatrical building. Greek and Roman plays remain some of the most powerful, moving, provocative, funny, biting, witty, and pertinent dramas with a lasting influence. They are living theatre, flourishing on stages around the world, moving beyond their traditional Western sphere of influence as directors explore their structural and thematic links with the performing arts of India, Korea, Indonesia, Africa, and Japan - to name only a few.

Theatrical drama started, according to the legend, in Athens, late in the sixth century BC by Thespis, who first had the idea to add speaking actors to the performances of choral song and dance, which occurred on many occasions throughout Greece by masked actors, performed before audiences outdoors, in daylight. This archaic way of theatrical performances inspired our research experiment, offering us the idea of replacing the actors' words in performances of Hellenic Drama with the international language of designs that express feelings and emotions and is the result of the emotional inputs by the drama presentation on the designer's creativity.

Theatrical Design

Theatrical design is an interdisciplinary and integrative process and a professional field of practice and applied research. Traditionally, it has been viewed as a service within the

organization of the theatre — not as a strategic resource towards the success of a performance. This traditional view of theatrical design is rapidly changing in our highly competitive age and it has become a feature of competitiveness and the creative discipline that coordinates data to produce positive innovation. The role of emotion is vital in any design discipline but it is absolutely impossible to ignore it in theatrical design. It is quite often that emotion, feelings, mood, motivation, are not well understood during the design process and the design acceptance, though we have evidence that attractive and pleasing things are best buys, work better, are media of easy learning, and produce better results. Also when designers are in a relaxed situation (positive emotion) they are more tolerant of designing difficulties and problems and what is recognized and accepted as a good design is usually in balance of beauty and usability.

Designers are continually searching for new design methods to communicate the emotional values of theatrical performances. In the new millennium Greek theatrical designers need to rethink the processes of designing and the ways in which they communicate the emotional values of the drama within the theatrical design. Design will operate as a leading discipline of performance innovation only if it will be able to incorporate the valuable knowledge of design emotion, design practice and design experience in a fluent process to the success of the performance. Stage designers should realize the importance, and support the involvement, of emotional experience in the design process in order to be the visionaries with important roles to play in the innovation process, and the key drivers to the performance success. Advances in their understanding of the influence of emotions, both on the designer during the designing process, and on the audience during performances, can change their operating parameters, enhance their creativity, make them more flexible and tolerant in finding innovative and aesthetic stage-design solutions. The research project is part of our efforts to offer a new perspective to Hellenic theatrical performances, which have been over the centuries of the greatest cultural value for Greece.

The case study

Our case study focuses on the possibilities of incorporating the strengths and the emotional powers of design, and mainly of textile design, in theatrical presentations and silent performances as a vital starting point for a new way of international dialogue and expression of ideas. The basic idea for our research collaboration derived from the fact that during the

last years, many theatrical designers in Greece have produced poor design results. Different factors contribute to success or failure, but often they can be traced back to the designers' designing ability or inability of innovative design approaches. Greek theatrical designers are gradually forced to bring more and more quality and innovation to their design proposals if they wish to be competitive.

The research team was composed of six qualified designers - staff members of the Textile Design Workshop of TEI of Athens, and interior design and textile design students. With the assistance of design innovation bodies, we investigated the possibility of a design theme that has common interest at a supranational level and can be undertaken and fulfilled together with other schools of design of different countries and cultures. Ancient Hellenic Drama, due to its qualities, was identified as the most suitable and appropriate to our experiment, a well-known subject not only to the Greek students but worldwide and of common interest. Forty-five students participated in our research. All the students had basic knowledge of the Hellenic Drama (Tragedy or Comedy) and of stage design. They were asked to create designs applicable to specific, active and well-known theatrical performances. The experiment was arranged in two major groups and in small ones of one, two or three participants, according to their personal wish, their level of theatre knowledge and their semester of attendance. All had to follow a similar work procedure that lasted the same time period. The experiment was repeated twice in two different periods with different groups of students.

Our didactic approach employed a data selection method by asking all participants to photograph or sketch all forms of designs and items that inspire them to visualize and create new design proposals for the specific presentations, defining their mental and emotional processing. Figure 1, is part of the photographic data that have inspired the students the costume designs.

Figure 1, Example of the participating students' selected photographic data. Ancient Hellenic female dresses, Terracotta, 5th century BC, National Museum, Athens.

Their project data derived:

- From data selected during the research part of the assignment and were accompanied by written protocols of the participants' impressions, emotions and ideas.
- From drawn materials produced during design sessions, accompanied by written protocols of the design procedure, of the inspiration and of their emotional state during the designing process.

Introductory sessions were considered as necessary to discuss the technical and design aspects, the organization and implementation of scenic, costume, lighting and sound design, of furniture, stage settings, and the techniques and technologies used to realize those designs on the stage. The second step was to expand our design sessions on costume design and construction, as well as on style, composition and also to encompass a discussion of aesthetics as it relates to the practical theatrical design. All designs sessions included short video, slide or image presentations of similar theatrical performances, so that the design process of the participants to be under the emotional influence of the dramatic theatrical atmosphere.

The following teaching and learning strategies were also used in relation to the project:

- Presentation of previous works via CD-ROMS, Internet, Videos, slides, transparencies and hard copies,
- Development of techniques that would assess the levels of creativity and innovation of our students and were targeting to new design approaches, through design teaching projects, design sessions, the study of theatrical design and of emotion driven design,
- Exploration of the role of research, of emotions and processes that lead to design innovation,
- Investigation on the possibilities of innovative designs and new design products that will result from the combined research of design, culture and today's accelerating technology,
- Production of designs for specific theatrical purposes and active performances, with examples of their proposed involvement,
- Presentation and evaluation of all the results and outcomes of the students' research and design works,
- Experimental performances.

An important issue was the involvement of all the participants in activities that allowed them to get close to information and gain access to data. They were assigned to inquire libraries, museums, archaeological sites, select information photos and slides on the Hellenic Drama, the Hellenic theatre and on theatrical performances; to attend performances and presentations in different theatre and places; to see videos and DVDs with international performances and presentations. A rapid virtual access to the places and people of their choice was offered to all of them, through a combination of activities and visits, as a part of their education programme.

After one semesters' work the participants proposed and presented designs and written protocols together with research on the possible ways of the designs implementation in the theatrical performances. We identified the selected works by classifying the designs and their mental and emotional experiences, outlining the different tools and activities used during the different stages of the assignment's fulfillment. The research team evaluated the design ideas and the design elements and the student sketches and representations were turned back accompanied with written remarks and statements, thus helping them to work on their proposals with the best possible practical results.

Various elements and constraints were considered including the design production cost. We categorized the sources of research, of interest, of inspiration; the emotional involvement on the selections of interests, of objects, of colors, of materials and media of work; the emotional involvement on the style of presentation, illustration and performance. The final design proposals were selected among hundred of sketches that were created during the project. A self-imposed restriction was necessary to our student enthusiasm, efforts and untiring energy, if chaos was to be avoided: to re-stain from the total spectrum of designs and to focus on those distinctively related to the character of the research. The implementation of our students' final design proposals in the experimental theatrical performances was accomplished with the assistance of multimedia.

The Outcomes

Our first presentation-performance took place into the premises of TEI of Athens as a first experimental approach, where the stage, the scenery and the costumes were made totally of yarns, textiles and papers (Figures 2, 3). Textile art has become an increasingly popular outlet for artistic expression among our design students in recent years. Formerly a preserve of professional trainees, the art of textile design is currently growing in appeal as design students discover its versatility, plasticity and power of expression, which are the qualities required by our experiment. So their selections were not the result of the participation of textile students among them, it was a conscious and emotional decision of the most appropriate medium for the particular experiment. The participating students, with joy and enthusiasm, presented a silent drama, using the “ emotional language of design” as medium that expresses words, feelings, action and “drama”.

Figure 2, From our performances; the costumes of the chorus

Figure 3, The scenery and the costumes are made totally of yarns, textiles and papers, creating a mythical world.

The use and synergy of modern technology played a vital and irreplaceable role, since all designs, expressing emotions and words, were presented via projectors and were accompanied by harmonic rhythms and selected sounds, thus embodying the actors and the scenery, generating a magical, magnetic and altogether mythical atmosphere, where the eyes became the gates of all kinds of feelings. Examples from the first experimental presentation, the costumes and the scenography are presented in figures 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7. The selected textile designs are inspired by ancient Hellenic prototypes, the scenery presents a mythical world (figure 3) and the costumes are transformations of the archaic female dress (figure 5 from figure 1).

Figure 4, from “Troades”. The chorus and the scenery are designed with the same square patterns and clear-bright colours expressing fear, pain, imprisonment and isolation.

Figure 5, Costume designed according to Figure 1.

Conclusion

The conclusions are many; the most important one for the future pathways of our research work is the presence and importance of colour - its importance often neglected in design disciplines. Colour was the focus-point, the key element and the strongest evidence of the influence of the different emotions involved in our experiment. Colour became for our students the medium of communication and the power of creation and expression of feelings and emotions involved in their performance. With their design and colour they expressed their thoughts and feelings, their hidden emotions, artistic anxieties and visions, their cultural heritage and identity. They actually proved that human emotions are strategic tools of design innovation and the designer an emotional dreamer. It is important to allow the designer to have not only an intellectual but also an emotional relation to the designing product, regardless its identity.

Colour is very important for life - a gray world would have been very sad and monotonous - since it influences our personality and our moods, and provides enjoyment and pleasure. It has been a powerful tool for humans from the cave era to nowadays, its perception being one of the first triumphs of the human intellect. In our design works, most of the time, we study and analyze design deeply, often forgetting the tremendous transformations that would occur - and do occur - with the use of colour, transformations that do not just influence forms and shapes, but mainly reflect the designers' inner emotional world. Within our experiment

colours, lines and shapes have defined passion, tranquility, happiness, anger, hate and all kind of feelings (figures 4, 6, 7) in an astonishing way.

Our successful educational synergy proved that players from distant cultures and production systems could create innovation that bears the hallmark of sensibility. We wish that our case study would provide a working model for developing future research projects through design education, which will involve universities, professors and students from multicultural backgrounds that have the same extensive design sensibility, feeling and vision. Our exploration hopes to stimulate further research on the processes in which the emotions of designers play an important role, and that the recently growing and enduring emphasis for emotion in design will be a future model on modern theatrical design applications that will open new horizons to young theatrical designers with sensibility and a spirit for innovation.

Figure 6, Media's fear, hate pain and passion is defined by colour.

Figure 7, Morning figures of chorus in purple and white are standing in front of a black wall;
from Euripides “Antigoni”

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